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Retail Sales Prediction for Rossmann Germany

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Evaluating FAIR Models for Rossmann Store Sales Prediction: Insights and Performance Analysis project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Dilara Cakmak will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Stores	https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.82556/nqeg-gy34	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License	no
R2	Train	https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.82556/yb6j-jw41	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License	no

R3	Test2	https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.82556/jerg-4b84	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License	no
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Description for "Stores":

supplemental information about the stores

Description for "Train":

historical data including Sales

Description for "Test2":

historical data excluding Sales

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Research Data Generation and Reuse Methods for Data Generation:

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA): Data was explored using statistical metrics (e.g., mean, median, variance) and visualizations (e.g., histograms, scatter plots) to understand the distributions and relationships between key variables, such as sales, number of customers, and store types.

Feature Engineering: To avoid bias, some observations were removed, and continuous variables were categorized. For example, CompetitionDistance was divided into 5 categories to better understand the impact of competition proximity on store performance. Stores farther from competitors generally showed higher sales and customer counts. A new variable, Avg Customer Sales, was created by dividing Sales by Customers. This helped highlight that StoreType A has the highest total sales and customers, while StoreType D had the best average spending per customer. StoreType B, with fewer stores, had the highest average number of customers. Promotions were found to significantly impact sales, with Promo leading to higher sales compared to Promo2, though no clear yearly trend was observed. Finally, outliers in the Sales data were removed to improve model accuracy.

Model Training: Various models were tested:

Linear Regression & Lasso Regression: Both achieved similar results, with R^2 values around 0.78 on the training and test sets.

Decision Tree: The basic model overfitted with R^2 of 0.9999 (train) and 0.9157 (test), but hyperparameter tuning improved it to 0.9635 (train) and 0.9354 (test).

Random Forest Regression: Performed the best, with R^2 of 0.9938 (train) and 0.9564 (test).

Random Forest and tuned Decision Tree showed the best performance, balancing accuracy and generalization.

Methods for Data Reuse:

Pre-existing Sales Data: The historical sales dataset for 1,115 Rossmann stores was reused. It included sales, customer count, store type, promotional status, holidays, and other related factors. The dataset was downloaded from Kaggle.

External Datasets: No additional external datasets were used, other than the original Kaggle dataset. However, future extensions might consider augmenting the dataset with external store or region-specific data.

Software Used:

Python: pandas for data manipulation and preprocessing (e.g., cleaning, aggregation). NumPy for numerical operations.

Jupyter Notebooks: Used for interactive analysis and visualization. matplotlib, seaborn, and plotly for generating plots (e.g., histograms, Implot, scatter plots).

Scikit-learn: For training machine learning models (e.g., Random Forest Regressor for forecasting) and perform hyperparameter tuning.

DBRepo3 API: Utilized for uploading, managing, and sharing datasets. Datasets were stored and metadata generated automatically by DBRepo.

Outputs:

Forecast Results:

Predicted sales outputs and corresponding error metrics are provided as .csv files. Each result file includes columns such as Id (store-date pair identifier) and Sales (predicted turnover in dollars).

Metadata describing the structure and units of these outputs is included to ensure reusability.

Scripts and Notebooks:

Full Python scripts (.py) and Jupyter Notebooks (.ipynb) are made available to reproduce, retrain, and evaluate the models. Each script is documented and adheres to reproducibility standards. Associated metadata (e.g., software requirements, runtime environment, and dependency versions) is captured in a codemeta.json file.

Model Artifacts:

Trained machine learning models are serialized as .pkl files and provided for reuse.

Each model artifact is described using FAIR-compliant metadata (ml:ModelArtifact entries), specifying model type (e.g., Random Forest, Linear Regression), training dataset identifiers, and serialization format (application/octet-stream).

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Decision makers in industry

Students and general public

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

Data Structure: The data is organized in a structured tabular format (CSV files), with each row representing sales data for a specific store and time period. Key features include store ID, date, sales, customers, promotions, and store type.

Versioning: To manage data versioning, each dataset version will be assigned a unique identifier (PID) when uploaded to DBRepo. This ensures that any updates or changes to the dataset are tracked, and the most recent version is always accessible.

Metadata

Name: The title of the dataset

Size: The size of the dataset

License: The terms under which the data is shared

Description: A summary of the dataset

Language: The language used in the dataset

Owner: Information about the dataset's creator, including ORCID iD if available

Schema: A description of the data structure

Versioning Information: The version of the dataset, indicated by a persistent identifier (PID)

Access to Database: Specifies the level of access available to the database

Engines: The platform used to host and manage the dataset, MariaDB: 11.1.3-debian-11-r6.

Keywords: Relevant terms to aid in searchability. This will help others to identify, discover, and reuse our data.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. Some datasets cannot be published and even need to be deleted at the end of the project. See section 5 for more details.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
0	Auth needed for DBRepo		Public	DBRepo	9627ec46-4ee6-4969-b14a-bda555fe34db	-
1	Auth needed for DBRepo		Public	DBRepo	b1c59499-9c6e-42c2-af8f-840181e809db	-
2	Auth needed for DBRepo		Public	DBRepo	7cbb845c-21dd-4b60-b990-afa8754a0dd9	-

Repository description: Rossmann operates over 3,000 drug stores in 7 European countries. Currently, Rossmann store managers are tasked with predicting their daily sales for up to six weeks in advance. Store sales are influenced by many factors, including promotions, competition, school and state holidays, seasonality, and locality. With thousands of individual managers predicting sales based on their unique circumstances, the accuracy of results can be quite varied.

My work includes various plots and graphs, visualizations, feature engineering, ensemble techniques, different ML algorithms with their respective parameter tuning, analysis, and trends. Predictions are of 6 weeks of daily sales for 1,115 stores located across Germany.

Methods or software needed to access and use data: To access and reuse the data, users will need access to the DBRepo platform. They must have DBRepo credentials (username and password) for authentication. No specific software is required beyond standard tools for data analysis (e.g., Python, Jupyter Notebook) once the data is downloaded via DBRepo.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be

published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns.

Data Description: Provided a comprehensive description of the dataset, including key variables, their meanings, and any transformations or feature engineering performed. This ensures users understand the context and structure of the data.

Data Preparation: Document the steps taken to preprocess the data, such as cleaning, handling missing values, and splitting the data into training, validation, and test sets. This helps others reproduce the analysis process.

Code Documentation: Explaining each step in the process. This includes data preprocessing, feature selection, model training, and evaluation. The Jupyter notebook (or Python script) will also be organized with clear section headers and explanations of each part of the process.

README: Included in the repository to provide an overview of the dataset and the analysis. It should explain the structure of the project, how to use the code, how to load the data, and how to interpret the results.

Results and Visualizations: Output results, such as performance comparison charts and evaluation metrics, will be included to validate the analysis and provide insights into the model's performance.

Reproducibility: To ensure that the analysis is reproducible, all code and documentation will be uploaded to a public repository in GitHub. Additionally, the dataset will be stored in a trusted repository of DBRepo.

Use of Metadata Fields in TUWRD: Will update and complete the metadata fields in the TUWRD platform to ensure that all necessary details (e.g., dataset version, authorship, licensing, and description) are available for reuse.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

In addition to the management of data, the project will also address the management of other digital research outputs, including software (e.g., scripts and Jupyter Notebooks), workflows, and predictive models developed during the project. These outputs will be documented within TUWRD, versioned, and shared in accordance with the FAIR principles (TUWRD). Clear metadata descriptions (e.g., schema:description), usage instructions, and licensing information (e.g., schema:license) will be included in the repository to facilitate discovery, access, interoperability, and reuse.

All software and workflows will be made openly available through trusted repositories such as GitHub, with each associated with persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs via Zenodo integration) (Github). Models developed during the project will be packaged, documented, and shared alongside the training datasets to ensure reproducibility. Any updates or changes to these outputs will be tracked using version control systems, and corresponding metadata will be updated accordingly in the repository.

Github: <https://github.com/Dilara520/rossmann-sales-predictions>

TUWRD: <https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/records/f5t2d-xt904>

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

All data management activities will be covered under the general operational support of the project team and institutional resources. No separate budget allocation for data management activities is required.

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with [the work package leaders] being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-

checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

All data will be stored and managed through DBRepo, a secure and reliable data repository platform. DBRepo provides version-controlled storage, ensuring that each update to the dataset is archived with a persistent identifier (PID).

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R1	writing	writing	reading only
R2	writing	writing	reading only
R3	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: The project owner (dataset uploader) and the DBRepo system administrators will have the rights to control access to the uploaded datasets. All datasets have been set to public visibility in DBRepo, but access management remains under the control of these roles if needed.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

We will follow the data management procedures of DBRepo and the TU Wien institutional policies. No additional national or funder-specific procedures are currently applicable. If new requirements arise, they will be incorporated accordingly.